

The Cultural Geography Perspective Of Zuoquan Folk Songs

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 26, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 28, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Cultural Geography, Zuoquan Folk Songs</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7778595</p>	<p>A song "Peach Blossom, Red, Apricot Blossom and White" lingers in the ridge of Taihang Mountain, and resounded through the land of Sanjin. As a beautiful name card of Shanxi folk songs, it spread all over the motherland, and Zuoquan folk songs were gradually well known to the world. The essence of Zuoquan Folk song — "flowering tune" is one of the first folk arts to be included in the national intangible cultural heritage list. Zuoquan folk song "Xiaohua Opera" was also included in the fourth batch of national intangible cultural heritage list in 2014. Plus liu to fish, Shi Zhan, JiAiFang, liu, liu quan singer plain, ZuoQuan folk song has become a typical representative of Shanxi folk songs, the classic "peach blossom red apricot blossom white""close Ge egg under the river wash clothes""brother""land home" and other works even became one of the Shanxi folk song symbols. In recent years, as the national increasing investment, the inheritance and protection of intangible cultural heritage in the important position of cultural construction, governments at all levels of publicity and promotion, especially the party's 20 report emphasizes the importance of inheriting Chinese excellent traditional culture, it also marks the mining of left folk songs, inheritance, protection and development to the history of the new height, new stage.</p>

Introduction

According to zuoquan county annals, ZuoQuan folk song is spread in zuoquan county, Shanxi Province and the surrounding areas of folk songs (Zhao Shiyuan, 1999), is the Zuoquan people collective creation in the production and living, directly reflect all kinds of scenes and phenomena of real life, real and vivid performance of ZuoQuan people's thoughts and feelings of song form (zhen-hua yao, 2011). After generation to generation, Zuoquan folk songs have become the most classic genre of folk music spread in Zuoquan County and its surrounding areas. Zuoquan folk song is different from the hequ folk songs and other folk songs, etc. It has clear and meaningful tunes, with rich poetic content and euphemistic and delicate style. Why is there such a huge difference between the folk songs bred by Zuoquan land and other Shanxi folk songs? It needs to find the answer from its geographical environment, historical development, cultural customs and people's life and labor?

Geographical Background

As the saying goes: "soil and water keep a song", our country vast, rich geological landscape and climate environment to different nationalities, different regions form different forms of music genres and styles of music, and all kinds of music genre also has a strong dependence on geographical environment, such as plateau mountain "folk songs", "song" along the river, "fishing", "grassland" pastoral ", rice area" field ", etc., these folk songs fully reflect the regional geographical features, is a direct product of specific geographical environment. Chinese famous music scholars Qiao Jianzhong (1987) in the 1980s put forward the concept of "land and song", after successively put forward "sound relationship" theory and music geography discipline construction idea, the traditional music and geographical environment, geographical distribution, social culture, discipline concept mutual penetration, integration development, concept is so far more than 30 years, far-reaching influence. Professor Qiao Jianzhong (1998) pointed out in his article on the Geographical Characteristics of Chinese Traditional Music and the Construction of Chinese Music Geography that "History has proved that in the development of traditional culture in different regions, relatively geographical factors, such as terrain, landform, location and climate, play the most stable and direct role".

Shanxi Province is located in the middle reaches of the Yellow River, in the east of the Loess Plateau, the second step of China's terrain plate. The whole territory is a longitudinal parallelogram, covering an area of 156,700 square kilometers. The surrounding Taihang Mountain, The Luliang Mountain, the Yellow River and the ancient Great Wall are separated from Hebei, Henan, Shaanxi and Inner Mongolia. It is recorded in the 28th year of Duke Xi, " After a successful battle, you will win a vassal. If it is not successful, the inner mountains and rivers, will be harmless also."Thus it can be seen that Shanxi is surrounded by mountains and rivers, with mountains and rivers as a barrier, which can be described as" the mountains and rivers ". The American ethnomusicologist Bruno Nettle (1961) pointed out: " Natural areas are clearly in line with music, and natural

barriers affect the boundaries of music."It is this natural barrier" inner mountains and rivers " that makes Shanxi less affected by the war, the population mobility is small, both material culture and intangible culture can be well preserved, and the traditional music produced has also formed obvious regional characteristics in terms of form and style.

Zuoquan County is located in the eastern edge of Shanxi Province, and the administrative division belongs to Jinzhong City, Shanxi Province. Zuo Quan stands on the ridge of Taihang Mountain, overlooking the North China Plain in the east and the land of Three Jin in the west, with steep terrain, rugged roads, boats and cars are difficult. It is the main traffic road to and from Shanxi and Hebei, and also the place for troops to gather. It is recorded in Zuoquan County Annals that the geographical coordinates of the jurisdiction of Zuoquan County are north latitude $36^{\circ}45'7'' - 37^{\circ}17'7''$, $113^{\circ}06'7'' - 113^{\circ}48'7''$ east longitude, and the county covers an area of 2028.1 square kilometers. The surrounding is bounded by the mountain, crossing the cross ridge in the east, bordering on Wuxiang Mountain in the west, Shiling in the south, and Zijing Mountain in the north (Zhao Shiyuan, 1999). The county has jurisdiction over five towns and five townships, namely Liaoyang Town, Macheng Town, Tongyu Town, Gua Town, Qin Town, Shixia Town, Shixia Township, Hanwang Township, Longquan Township, Suyu Township, Yangjiao Township, with 379 administrative villages with a total population of more than 144,500 people (the seventh National Population Census, 2021).

Figure 1. Administrative division map of Zuoquan County

From the point of view of cultural geography, China with large and small hinggan mountains, the central taihang, qinling, dabashan and southern ling, big LouShan, WuMengShan boundary is divided into two parts, and left county is located in the hinterland of the taihang mountains, located in the edge of the line, belong to the "plateau culture area" and "plain culture area" border zone, loess, ravines, the people here is given priority to with individual work, this is the ideal scene of singing folk songs, is the basic premise of folk genre, and the working people are also the best of folk songs. Therefore, most of Zuoquan folk songs belong to the type of folk songs, improvised lyrics, the singing form is mainly solo, and the structure is mostly the opposite sentence pattern, or two sentences expanded or repeated, with function words and lining words. However, different from other regions, the folk songs are loud and loud, with a long and free rhythm and jump into obvious characteristics. The melody of Zuoquan folk songs does not fluctuate much, and the rhythm is orderly, except for the large cavity, and the drag of the music color is flexible and changeable, close to life.

In the Book of Geography, The Book of Han: " rigid, soft and urgent, different sounds, is the ethos of soil and water."It can be seen that geographical factors such as geology, environment, climate and other factors not only determine the production and living style of the local people, but also determine the regional color of the music culture in the region. Over time, a relatively stable music style has been formed. According to the difference of music color, Shanxi music culture can be divided into four color areas, namely, Jinzhong music color area, Jinnan music color area, southeast Shanxi music color area and North Shanxi music color area. The so-called "music color area" refers to the spread area of folk songs with some main common musical style characteristics (Miao Jing, Qiao Jianzhong, 1987). Under the concept of music geography, Zuoquan folk song belongs to Jinzhong music color area, which is the most brilliant part of Jinzhong music color area. As shown in Figure 2, the music color area of Jinzhong focuses on the Jinzhong Basin, covering most of the central Shanxi. It

is located in the hinterland of Shanxi, and the music is less influenced by other provinces, so the music forms are distinct and very representative, among which zuoquan folk songs and Qitai Yangko are the most prominent.

Figure 2 Distribution map of folk songs in Jinzhong color area

In deep taihang mountains and tender qing get a water protection, ZuoQuan area vegetation, life is not rich, but the people life stability, less affected by war, in the geographical environment of the traditional folk music style is flexible, rich in change, "flowering" lyrics ingenious, anything can "blossom", also from the side reflects the left people relatively stable living conditions and positive and optimistic hopeful attitude towards life. In contrast, the "mountain qu" in the music color area of northern Shanxi presents the characteristics of vast and thick, rough and powerful, and wide sound range. The reason is that the hequ is located in the alpine mountainous area, with harsh natural environment, dry and sandy, and there is no place to rely on. People have to rely on "walking to the west" to make a living. Both Shanxi folk songs, they have such huge differences in styles. It can be seen that this is not only the personal choice of folk song singers, but also the result of the direct effect of geological landform and natural environment.

In addition, Zuoquan County has a temperate continental climate with four distinct seasons and large annual temperature difference, With sunshine of 2570 hours all year round and annual average precipitation of 538 mm, which provides suitable temperature, light and precipitation for crop growth. Zuoquan County is high in the northwest and low in the southeast. Such a drop makes here have both the large temperature difference between day and night in the mountainous area, and the water source and tidal flats brought by the Qingzhang River running through it, forming a unique microclimate. From the aspects of production mode and output crops, Zuoquan County belongs to the millet area, the people's production mode is mainly agricultural production, the main food crops are corn, millet, beans, wheat, oats, sorghum, etc., cash crops are potato, sunflower, walnut, persimmon, pepper, chestnut, hemp, vegetables, etc., walnut, persimmon, pepper; the county also grew 318 kinds of wild medicinal materials, such as forsythia, Dangshen, Astragalus, pleurum and so on. The northwest is high, shrubs and mountain meadows, suitable for the development of animal husbandry, carrying 400,000 sheep.

Figure 3 Industrial layout plan diagram of Zuoquan County

Zuoquan folk songs as the folk improvisation in the fields of folk music form, is the reality of the production and living, influenced by the thought of the farmers, a large part of the labor songs reflect the profound farming culture, such as "spring song""field song", "pick rice""pick pepper" pick walnut "pod" persimmon red "etc., and in the lyrics of the folk songs also work everywhere and" yam egg ", " bean pod ", " pepper ", " buckwheat ", " needle ", " sorghum ", " persimmon ", " walnut ", " medicine " and other crops.

Historical Background

Shanxi is one of the earliest cultural birthplaces of the Chinese nation, known as the "cradle of Chinese civilization". China, the first emperor of Shanxi as the main activity area; Yao, Shun, Yu in Pingyang (now Shanxi Province), Anyi (now Shanxi Province); the first slavery regime — Xia Dynasty was born here; in the Spring and Autumn period, Jin in Shanxi, Jin Wen ranked one of the five hegemony... Zuo Quan in the thick history of Shanxi, also has a long history and culture. In the 1980s, archaeological workers found a large number of pottery pieces, stone axes, bone arrowheads and other cultural relics in the north cultural site and Huanglong Cave of Majiaping Village. These cultural relics retained in the Neolithic period marked that our ancestors as early as more than 4,000 years ago, have lived on this land. According to "Li, month", "Shi Ji · Chu family", "Han Book · five elements", "Liao State annals" and other historical records, "ancient five emperors Zhuanxu son Zhu Rong seal in Yang", here refers to "Yang", is the first "Jizhou"; Tang Yao not changed; Yushun into Jizhou; Shang after Jizhou; West Zhou Tang; Jin in the Spring and Autumn period; early Han after Zhao; the Qin Dynasty in Shangdang County; in the Eastern Han Dynasty as "He County"; in the Northern Wei Xiaochang years Liaoyang County (Wang Xizhe, 1991). After thousands of years, wars continued frequently, dynasties changed, and the county system was repeatedly merged and changed, which became known as he, Yang, Liaoyang, Liao Mountain, Liao Prefecture and Liao County.

"September 18 Incident" the Japanese invasion, occupied the east of Liao County, set up Liaoxi County. After the July 7 Incident in 1937, the headquarters of the 129th Division of the Eighth Route Army and the Hebei, Henan and Shanxi Provincial Committee of the Communist Party of China set up a committee in Liao County and established the Anti-Japanese base in Taihang Mountain. In 1940, the eighth route army headquarters moved to liao county, and stationed for five years, so liao county become the communist party, the eighth route army in north China behind the war of political, military, economic, cultural center, zhu, deng xiaoping, peng dehuai, liu, Zuoquan, Luo Ruiqing, xu Xiangqian the older generation of proletarian revolutionaries in this fighting, live for a long time. On May 25, 1942, when General Zuo Quan, deputy chief of staff of the Eighth Route Army, fought against the Japanese "mopping up", he died in Mashan Maling, Liao County, at the age of 37. In order to commemorate the general Zuo Quan and the people to let the later generations remember the heroic feat of the Chinese nation, the people renamed "Liao County" to "Zuoquan County" on September 18 of the same year.

Music is a history of flow, recording the development and evolution of The Times. Admittedly, the changes of society, the influence of the system, the integration of the nation and the changes of The Times will affect the content conveyed by music and the variation of musical form, and also make some musical form

progress or die out. At present, the Zuoquan folk songs that can be verified are just like a thick history book. When you open a page, frames of history will appear on the paper...

In the old feudal society with harsh natural environment and low productivity, the toiling people received the ruthless exploitation of the feudal class, coupled with the aggression and wanton division of the imperialist powers in the late Qing Dynasty, the people lived in dire straits. "Eating Foreign Smoke" reflects the British powers in China during the reign of Daoguang, which not only destroyed the health of the people, but also destroyed their children and women. Lin Zexu, the governor of Guangdong and Guangdong, was upright, honest and honest. In Humen, Humen in 1893. The vigorous anti-smoking movement awakened the patriotic consciousness of the Chinese people, and this historical moment was also widely praised by the people. Under the feudal society of women under the bondage of the "four rights" and oppression, physical and mental pain and weakness, "cry husband" with the perspective of the husband died landlord call, hungry cold can only send daughter to do child bride, reflect his difficult life, also revealed the nature of the landlord class cruel and greed.

During the Anti-Japanese War, in July 1939, the 769 Regiment of the 358 Brigade and the 2nd Independent Regiment of the Eighth Route Army fought fiercely with the Japanese army in the Langya Mountain in Shixia Village, killing more than 100 Japanese soldiers. The famous Zuo Quan folk song "There is a Langya Mountain in the Stone Box" (also known as "Langya Mountain Battle") came into being and was widely circulated. In 1942, in order to cover the transfer of the headquarters, general Zuo Quan died in the cross Ridge siege battle, and set up a "Taihang heroism handed down through the ages" monument. In order to commemorate general Zuo Quan, the people spontaneously compiled and sang the folk song "General Zuo Quan" and sang it throughout the county. The establishment of the Taihang Mountain Anti-Japanese base area and the headquarters of the Eighth Route Army is the most colorful one in Zuoquan County, And the Zuoquan folk songs during the Anti-Japanese War, For example, "Revenge for General Zuo Quan", "Hundred Regiments", "Red Fortress", "Escape", "Rectification of the Three Winds", "Land Return", "Convention on supporting the Army", "Production economy" and so on, be too numerous to enumerate, With a short and lean structure, catchy melodies, and sincere and rustic lyrics, It recorded the flames of the Anti-Japanese War, difficult times, current affairs and politics, laws and policies, military-civilian relations, self-rescue production, war culture and other all-round contents, Concondensed the most bright red of the revolutionary struggle, Has been sung for generations.

After the founding of new China, a new historical era was opened up. The broad masses of the people completely overthrew the oppression of the "three great mountains" and ended the history of more than a hundred years of humiliation. In the form of composing folk songs, the Zuoquan people recorded the construction of factories and mines in the early days, the successful completion of the "first five-year Plan" and the "second five-year Plan", showing that under the leadership of the Communist Party, the people of all ethnic groups were independent and self-reliant and worked hard to build the motherland. In 1965, the third National People's Congress put forward the grand goal of "four modernizations", and "Singing the Four modernizations" sang the aspirations of the left people to support the leadership of the Party and respond to the call of the Party. Since the reform and opening up, the whole country has been full of vitality, the productive forces have been newly liberated, the problem of food and clothing for 1.1 billion people has been basically solved, and a moderately prosperous society has been achieved. "Persimmon red" in a song so sing: " red persimmon round and fat, taste a persimmon sweetheart, sisters like to pick harvest fruit, happy life million long." Zuoquan people with simple language, sincere songs, to praise today's happy life. In recent years, people's living standards and on a new level, feeling, happiness, security more substantial, more secure, more sustainable (" the central committee of the communist party of China about the party's major achievements in one hundred and historical experience resolution, 2021), with many reflect the successful Olympic Games, win the battle poverty hot politics of folk songs, popular, widely sung. For example, the left power folk songs record the history of the left power people, tell the story of the left power people, and integrate the lives of the left power people into the bones and blood of the left power people.

cultural background

Zuoquan County is located in the Taihang Mountain area, the economic development is slow, the people face the loess back to heaven and earth farming, with sweat for to maintain the continuation of life return. Thousands of years of hard work and self-sufficiency have cultivated the feelings of the left people, such as simplicity and advocating nature, and also imprinted on the blood many virtues, such as thrift, hardship and hardworking, respecting the old and caring for the young, supporting the family and helping others. It is recorded in the Annals of Liao Prefecture · Old Preface: " His practice is especially diligent, and his custom is simple, with the legacy of the Tang dynasty." He said, " Therefore, the three provinces, while Liao County is the most... The people can be round, straight, not smart, and sophisticated, not luxurious." It can be seen that Zuoquan County has been industrious, simple, honest and honest good folk customs since ancient times, and even today, this is also the case.

Thanks by the unique geological landform and historical culture, Zuoquan has gradually formed its own unique production customs, living customs, etiquette customs, festival customs, dialect customs and other

customs, and also formed folk art forms such as folk songs, small opera, piano shu and shehuo, and showed its unique regional style.

Folk songs are an important part of the traditional Chinese national music and culture, with a rich historical accumulation. Shanxi is known as the "sea of folk songs", and has a long history of folk song development. At present, there are more than two or twenty thousand folk songs in Shanxi, among which "hit the soil song": " sunrise, the sun and rest, dig Wells and drink, plow and eat, how can the emperor power to me!"For the folk songs of Yao period, showing the daily labor and life style of ordinary people in a colloquial way, and praising the beauty of rural life. Guo Maoqian in the Song Dynasty compiled "Yuefu Poems": " establish my common people, mo bandit water, do not know, shun the emperor."It is also the folk song of the Yao period, which shows that under the governance of Emperor Yao, the people have ample food and clothing, and live and work in peace and contentment. According to legend, the Song of the South Wind written by Emperor Shun said: " The smoke of the south wind can relieve the anger of our people. When the south wind, you can enrich the people."To express ambition, with the warm" south wind " compared to the benevolent government and good government, can warm all things, blessing the people. In addition, China's earliest total collection of poetry in the book of songs "wind", including the folk songs around 160, including "tang feng" and "wei feng" most collected from the ancient Shanxi folk, such as "tang feng" in the "silk", "pepper chat", "bustard feather", "feng" wei " rat " Fen fall ", sandalwood "Ge Ju", etc. These folk songs have a wide range of themes, reflecting love and marriage life, praising labor, telling sorrow, complaining about the dark rule of the ruling class, etc. They are a mirror of the life of the common people, and express the beautiful vision of the ancient working people to resist the oppression of the ruling class and pursue a happy life. Under the influence of such a profound folk song background in Shanxi Province, Zuoquan folk songs also developed and grew earlier.

The production of Zuoquan folk songs can not be separated from the folk custom of "making she fire". Since ancient times, Zuoquan has had the traditional custom of "making she fire", and the Ming and Qing dynasties were more extensive. During festivals, offering sacrifices to gods or temple fairs, especially on the first day and the fifteenth day of the first lunar month, every family sets up lights and sets up fire. Taking the village as the unit, the people held a ceremony of worship in front of the Temple of Sanguan, and performed "Wen Shehuo" and "Dance Shehuo" one after another. After that, they went from street to street, calling it "walking all diseases", which has the meaning of eliminating disasters and praying for happiness. At the same time, a variety of collective cultural activities, Yangko, dance, small dance, lion dance, dragon lantern, walking on stilts, rowing land boat, running bamboo horse, pavilion, drum, back stick, Yellow River array and other traditional folk skills have come on stage, the people entertain themselves, lively. In the process of "making Shehuo", folk artists used to sing historical allusions or local events into folk songs and mix them into various programs for performances. As time passed, they became popular. It is said that in the Song Dynasty, every village had a group performing shehuo programs, and the Ming and Qing Dynasties were more popular. Later, it was passed down from generation to generation and continued to this day, providing people with spiritual enjoyment in the gap between labor.

In material civilization is relatively barren, citizen economy underdeveloped taihang mountains, folk songs became the people work interval, one of the few entertainment, people by the folk songs to describe life, express emotion, impart knowledge, record history, folk songs in the most important position in the traditional culture. Zhang Zhongyin's poem Liaoyang City in the Song Dynasty wrote: " Zhuanxu was regardless of the year, and the mountains and rivers were still tilted. Holy Dynasty culture and education of the quilt, string chanting family rites and music."The Ming Dynasty Wanli" Liao State Annals "recorded:" in the top of the Taihang Mountain, in the mountains, but the poor, but the remote songs, and the style of writing is quite prosperous."It can be seen that since the Song and Yuan Dynasties, the people of Liaoning Prefecture have formed a trend of singing folk songs, and every family, men and women, have the habit of" string reciting " folk songs. Folk songs are the foundation of traditional Zuoquan's music culture. Many of the Zuoquan folk songs and dances, opera music, rap music, folk instrumental music, religious music, etc., are gradually formed, developed and changed directly or indirectly on the basis of Zuoquan folk songs.

After the outbreak of the Anti-Japanese War, the people is the folk political and propaganda function to the extreme, a passionate or beautiful, or touching, or envy evil or lively ZuoQuan folk song arises at the historic moment, greatly meet the spiritual needs of the eighth route army soldiers and the general public, will also be important message, signal secretly into the lyrics, transfer information, record history. The eight-year War of Resistance against Japanese aggression catalyzed the revolutionary emotion of the left right people's loyalty to the Party and hatred towards the enemy, thus forming a natural plot full of dedication and sacrifice. Such precious spirit is also reflected in the folk songs created by the people collectively. Wartime ideas dominated the dominant position in the left and became the dominant tone of the left culture, and the psychology of hatred and revenge evolved into a kind of judging by the enemy, right and wrong, simply rejecting foreign, new and foreign things, and built a stubborn psychological front, which is shaped like and lovely; its quality is one-sided

(Ma Yanping, 2004). This sense of dependence and group passion restrict the development of left power economy to some extent, but it has a positive significance in protecting traditional culture.

Today's Zuoquan, everyone is a folk singer, and people regard "people sing well" as the highest praise, which is far more enviable than who has more money and wide land. Singing folk songs and dancing opera also once became an important condition for men to find objects and their in-laws and daughter-in-law. Now the left down the left folk songs are all classics, the left people have already integrated the left folk songs into the bones, into the blood. Fundamentally, the "high quality" of Zuoquan folk songs is due to the high "cost" invested in the "production process". He or she turns her life's pain, the hatred, and the wound into only a few songs (Tian Qing, 2000). As the saying goes, "folk songs are just poor villages". The more remote and closed places, the more likely to contain rich folk music (Qiao Jianzhong, 2009). To some extent, the temporary backwardness of economic development is a good condition for retaining the traditional culture. This is well explained in economically developed areas in our country, such as Shenzhen, Shanghai, Guangzhou and other economically developed areas, it is difficult to find the figure of traditional folk songs, and Yunnan, Guizhou, Shanxi, shaanxi, Ningxia, Qinghai, Guangxi, Xinjiang, Tibet, Inner Mongolia and other economic underdeveloped areas, but contains rich treasure of folk songs.

In conclusion, zuoquan in the unique geographical environment, a long history, simple cultural customs under the influence of the northern folk songs loud and bold and unrestrained distant wind and southern folk songs, graceful, formed its own unique style, its scale, tone, backbone, melody, rhythm rhythm has obvious characteristics, unique, unique, and well preserved, sing in Shanxi, to the country, to show the world the "hometown of Chinese folk art".

Origin And Development

The development history of Zuoquan folk songs can be roughly divided into six stages: germination stage, formation period, development period, prevalence period, decline period and remodeling period.

The fire of ancient mythology ignited the belief of thousands thousand years. In today's zuoquan county north fire mountain, on the basis of the original fire temple site rebuilt the temple, according to the steps of the mountain to a vigorous hall, temple to a 3.3 meters high white marble statue, he is one of the myth of the ancient five emperor xu xu son —— harmony, because of its fire by later honored as vulcan. According to the Annals of Yuanfeng Nine Regions in the Northern Song Dynasty, "Liaoyang City was built by urong, the son of Zhuangxu", so urong was respected as an ancestor by the people of Zuo Quan. It can be imagined that the ancient people who paid attention to sacrificial activities once held ancient Musical Instruments, singing and dancing, praying for their ancestors to bless the coming year and give them light and happiness. This was the germination of the early Zuoquan folk songs.

The Song and Yuan dynasties were the gestation and formation of the two major music streams in the north and south of China (Wang Baiu, 2004). Shanxi was an important stronghold of Beiqu, and Zuoquan folk songs were also traced back at this time. Zuoquan folk songs "cavity" genre part of the works song card structure and the song dynasty "earn" and "loose" has many similarities, with qu card lyrics, a number of song card compose, affected by the "palace tune", the same palace rhyme to the end, the structure of the former is composed of introduction, positive and end of small set, and the latter is also composed of overture, positive and end three parts, and retained a large number of ancient timbre and rhythm. This shows that the song dynasty citizen class, the development of economic drive citizens growing music, folk music gradually to opera, stage art development, Zuoquan area by its traffic block, the citizen economy is not developed, keep it in the form of folk songs, like "music fossil", let us in one thousand later today can hear the voice of the ancient. The more shorter "minor" and "miscellaneous" songs "are derived, changed and developed from the folk activities of" making Shehuo ", forming a folk song that is close to life, lively and easy to sing. The poem "Liaoyang City" written by Zhang Zhongyin, a poet of the Song Dynasty mentioned in the previous article, also clearly states that the people of Liaoyang had the habit of "comparing hu string songs" during the Song Dynasty, and the above is the formation period of Zuoquan folk songs.

During the Ming and Qing dynasties, folk music developed unprecedented development. During this period, various kinds of sacrificial activities, temple fairs, traditional festivals and folk performances spontaneously organized by the common people have provided a broad platform for the integration and development of various art categories. In particular, the folk song ditty achieved unprecedented development in the Ming Dynasty and became a major feature of the Ming Dynasty music. In the end of the Ming Dynasty, Shen Defu recorded in "Wanli Wild Huo Compilation · Fashion Small Order": " Folk song songs do not ask the north and South, men and women, the old and young good and cheap, and everyone likes to listen to them, so that the publication of the world, refreshing, refreshing."This can see one of the folk music activities. The historical imprint of Zuoquan folk songs can also be found in the poems of Wujun Mountain and Liaoyang Crazy Poems written by the Ming and Qing Dynasties. During the Ming and Qing dynasties, folk songs were widely spread in Liaoyang County, with the characteristics of "popularization" and "secularization". They deeply reflected the real life of the people in different forms, different styles, different rhythm, easy to accept

and sing, and became an important way for the people to relax and entertain and convey feelings. During this period, many traditional folk songs were produced, and there are still some classic works such as "Embroidery Bag", "Make Five More", "Eating Foreign Smoke" and "Little Black Mouse on the Oil Lantern".

The "May 4 th" New Culture Movement that broke out in 1919 was a patriotic movement of the Chinese people completely against the emperor and the seal. The rise of the new culture movement also injected new strength into the development of Zuoquan folk songs. In this period, the lyrics and tunes of Zuoquan folk songs were increasingly improved and perfected, and their ideas were more profound. There also emerged works against feudal ideas such as "Liu Mei Hiding in Marriage", "Foot" and "Crying Husband".

During the War of Resistance against Japanese Aggression, Liao County, as the cultural center of the Communist Party and the Eighth Route Army adhering to the war of resistance behind the enemy lines in North China, established the policy of "literature and art serving politics and serving the people". A large number of literary and art workers also gathered here, which provides objective conditions for the further development of Zuoquan folk music. In early 1940, the Liao County propaganda team was established. In July 1941, the Southeast Jin Federation of Literary and Art established clubs, cultural cooperatives, cultural canteens, etc., and also held photography exhibitions and woodcut exhibitions. Theater troupes and propaganda teams at all levels of the county went deep into the fields and held artistic activities to develop cultural undertakings behind the enemy lines in rich and diverse ways. Literature and art work in order to better carry out the anti-japanese national salvation work, go to the people, and the local people, explore traditional folk songs, on the basis of the original folk tunes fill in new words, old bottle new wine, to grafting, filling, modification, deep, innovation, create the propaganda anti-japanese, unity, signal follow the pace of resistance left folk songs. This is also the period when Zuoquan folk songs produce the most, The richness of its content, Fully show the flames of war, difficult times, current affairs and politics, laws and policies, military-civilian relations, production and self-rescue, battlefield culture and other contents, at the same time, Huangfu Shuyu, Wang Shuxian, Hao Naiwu, Yan Lifu, Hu Zhirui, Bai Jianqing and other literary and artistic workers also systematically organized the folk songs, Print and print the collected folk songs into a book, In 1943, it compiled and printed "Liaoxi County Small Collection"; In 1945, it was impeded on hemp paper, Included more than 80 folk songs; In 1946, "Left Right minor Collection", It includes 105 folk songs.

Zuoquan folk songs conform to the development of The Times, but they also have been restricted by The Times. During the ten years of the "Cultural Revolution", a large number of rebel songs, quotations songs and model operas were filled with all musical activities, while the development of other culture and art stagnated. During this period, all the cultural system of Zuoquan County participated in the "Cultural Revolution", and all subordinate units were fully seized, and the leading group of the Cultural Revolution was established. Many performing arts groups were delegated for labor training and received re-education of the poor and middle peasants. Zuoquan folk songs were more regarded as "poisonous grass" and "bad word tone", and literary and art workers became "ox ghosts and snake gods", which were mercilessly criticized and persecuted, and Zuoquan folk songs thus entered a period of decline. But the vitality of folk songs is tenacious, it comes from the broad masses of the people, and has not disappeared in the lives of the people...

The great social change is inevitably accompanied by the evolution and remodeling of culture. After the Third Plenary Session of the 11th Central Committee, the Party and the state shifted their focus to socialist modernization, opening a new chapter of reform and opening up. Under the guidance of the ideological line of "emancipating the mind and seeking truth from facts", the Party and the state attach great importance to cultural construction, and timely adjust the principles and policies of literary and art work. Cultural and artistic undertakings across the country flourish like bamboo shoots after a spring rain. Under the call of the state, Zuoquan County has established cultural centers, art galleries, art troupes, clubs, various troupes, cultural stations, cultural propaganda teams and art activities and art training classes, cultural performances and competitions, and cultural exhibitions in the middle of the county, and organized the monthly publication, and was rated as "the Hometown of Chinese Folk Art" by the Ministry of Culture by the Ministry of Culture.

Conclusion

With the further development of market economy, cultural activities tend to develop market-oriented, and Zuoquan folk songs are protected, reshaped and developed in this period. The county party committee and government take Zuoquan folk songs and Zuoquan flower opera as the name card of promoting Zuoquan culture, and build them in an all-round way, and the mass folk singing activities are more popular. Newly created Zuoquan folk songs are constantly emerging, and their ideological content closely follows the national ideology and the theme of The Times. At the same time, a hundred flowers bloom, both aesthetic and secular, and the theoretical level and artistic level have been greatly improved. ZuoFeng, Zhao Lianqing, get a sound of literary and art workers to further ZuoQuan folk songs, sorting and creation, successively published "ZuoQuan folk songs" (1980), "minor tone battle song epic" (1986), the choice of Anti-Japanese war folk songs "(1987)," ZuoQuan folk songs integration "(1990)," peach blossom red apricot blossom white —— left folk songs " (2004), including a large number of ZuoQuan folk songs. Led by the government department, the release of

"Zuoquan Folk Songs" (1998) tape, "Peach Blossom, red, apricot blossom and White" (2002), "Take Your Time" (2002) MTV CD. Representative of Zuoquan folk songs left people singer in all kinds of national and provincial joint performance, literature and art competition for excellent results, various media widely reported, and emerge liu fish, Hao Yulan, Zhao Sanzhu, ji aifang, Li Mingfang, Shi Zhanming, Liu Hongqing, liu, GuanLifang, Cao Yanming a large number of outstanding folk singer.

Since the beginning of the new century, the artistic status, performance form, singing level and popular scope of Zuoquan folk songs have reached a new level. Zuoquan County, the "Taihang Pearl", has also been known to the world, and has successfully held national folk song competitions such as "the Second China North and South Folk Song Challenge Competition" and "Zuoquan Folk Song Collection · International Folk Song Competition". In particular, the "Zuoquan Folk Songs · 2019 International Folk Song Competition" gathered domestic top singers and scholars, the number of applicants reached 2,079, and the number of live viewers of the event reached 300 million, triggering a "Zuoquan fever". This is not only a singing competition, but also a large-scale cultural activity that Shanxi Province includes into the overall strategic deployment in order to achieve high-quality transformation and development.

Reference

Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. V. (2006). *Research in education* (10th ed.). Pearson.

Burnsed, C. V., & Eppers, S. (1997). The effects of viewing videotaped music performances on the perception of the elements of music. *Applications of Research in Music Education*, 15(2), 13-18.

Ellis, M. (1999). Spoken responses about music excerpts before and after a course in music appreciation. *Contributions to Music Education*, 26(1), 7-32.

Ellis, M. (2002). Student perceptions of the effects of a course in music appreciation. *Contributions to Music Education*, 29(2), 67-83.

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